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Review article

Navigating the dual burden of dental and periodontal care in individuals who also smoke: an expert review

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: Smoking poses a significant challenge to oral health, particularly in individuals with dental and periodontal disease. This expert review explores the dual burden of managing periodontal and dental care in smokers, emphasizing the impact of chronic tobacco exposure on disease progression and treatment outcomes. **Study Selection, Data, and Sources:** Clinical trials, systematic reviews, and international guidelines were consulted where available. Search terms specific to the topic were entered into PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar to identify the most relevant literature.

Results: Chronic smoking accelerates biofilm re-accumulation and periodontal tissue destruction, complicating treatment outcomes. Smoking cessation remains the most effective strategy for mitigating these risks, improving healing, reducing inflammation, and restoring microbiota balance. Dental professionals play a crucial role in integrating smoking cessation support into periodontal care through evidence-based interventions such as behavioral counseling, pharmacotherapy, and harm reduction strategies. Emerging technologies, including mobile health applications and remote monitoring, enhance patient engagement in smoking cessation efforts. Alternative nicotine products, such as e-cigarettes and heated tobacco products, may serve as harm reduction tools for smokers unwilling to quit, though their long-term effects on oral health remain unclear.

Conclusions: A multidisciplinary approach that combines periodontal therapy with tailored smoking cessation interventions is essential for improving oral health outcomes in smokers. Future research should prioritize longitudinal studies to assess the effectiveness of integrated smoking cessation and periodontal treatment strategies.

Abbreviations: NRTs, Nicotine replacement treatments; HTPs, Heated tobacco products; ONPs, Oral nicotine pouches.

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Clinical Relevance: The integration of smoking cessation into routine dental care is essential to improve treatment outcomes and long-term oral health. This review emphasizes the need for evidence-based strategies to manage smokers in dental settings and highlights the importance of further research to refine clinical guidelines.

1. Introduction

Tobacco consumption remains a global health issue, impacting 1.3 billion individuals and leading to more than 7 million deaths each year mainly due to diseases directly linked to smoking [1], including lung cancer, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and cardiovascular conditions [2,3].

Additionally, tobacco consumption and cigarette smoking significantly increases the risk of oral cancer due to the presence of carcinogenic compounds in tobacco, which promote malignancy through multiple biological mechanisms [4]. Smoking also exacerbates oral and dental health conditions, including a higher prevalence of dental caries [5], due to reduced salivary flow and altered oral microbiota. Furthermore, smoking promotes the accumulation of dental plaque and calculus [6,7], fostering an environment conducive to the onset and progression of periodontal disease [8,9]. Depending on the definition of disease and smoking exposure, the risk of developing destructive periodontal disease is 5 to 20 times higher in smokers compared to never-smokers. The dose-response relationship between cigarette consumption and periodontal disease severity further strengthens the evidence for the harmful effects of tobacco smoke [8,10]. Chronic exposure to tobacco smoke also results in progressive tooth staining and discoloration [11–13], negatively affecting aesthetic appearance and self-confidence. Additionally, smoking is a major contributor to halitosis [14], as it disrupts the balance of oral microbiota, further compounding its detrimental effects on oral health.

Encouragingly, smoking cessation dramatically reduces the risk of these conditions and promotes improved oral health outcomes. Quitting smoking leads to reduced inflammation, enhanced periodontal healing, and a rebalancing of the oral microbiota, ultimately lowering the risk of oral cancer and periodontal disease while preventing further tissue damage [15–19]. Tailored cessation programs that integrate smoking reduction with enhanced oral hygiene strategies offer synergistic benefits for both oral and overall health [20].

Individuals with periodontal disease who smoke exhibit a distinct phenotype, characterized by the combined detrimental effects of elevated bacterial load due to poor oral hygiene and toxins from cigarette smoke. This dual burden not only exacerbates periodontal tissue damage but also accelerates disease progression, leading to compromised healing following periodontal therapy.

The interplay between tobacco-induced chronic oxidative stress and the proliferation of pathogenic oral bacteria creates a highly destructive environment, further impairing oral tissue repair and increasing susceptibility to infections. This is particularly concerning for individuals already suffering from conditions such as gingivitis or periodontal disease, as smoking acts as a disease-modifying factor, significantly worsening disease severity [21].

Reducing exposure to cigarette smoke remains a public health priority, particularly for individuals with preexisting oral health conditions, where minimizing or ideally eliminating smoking is crucial. Tailored interventions that address both smoking cessation and enhanced oral hygiene could significantly mitigate the compounded risks associated with cigarette consumption and poor oral health.

The American Dental Association (ADA), the World Dental Federation (FDI) and the World Health Organization (WHO) emphasize that dental practices provide a unique and effective setting for smoking recognition, prevention, and cessation [22–24]. Integrating smoking cessation into routine oral healthcare is vital, as research consistently shows that quitting smoking leads to significant improvements in oral health over time.

This review offers current and emerging clinical insights into the dental and periodontal management of individuals who smoke, equipping dental professionals with evidence-based strategies to address these complex cases. Drawing from multidisciplinary expertise, the authors propose an integrated approach incorporating behavioral counseling, clinical pharmacology, oral care strategies, smoking cessation interventions, and medical education. This comprehensive framework aims to improve patient outcomes and advance oral health care for smokers.

2. Methods

The databases used to identify the most relevant papers were PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar, using the keywords "smoking," "cigarette," or "tobacco" combined with specific dental terms including "periodontal," "dental implant," "peri-implant," "dental cleaning," "caries," and "dental color." Particular attention was given to clinical trials, systematic reviews, and international guidelines. Animal and in vitro studies were excluded. However, this review is not intended to be a systematic review. Instead, it is structured as an expert review, prioritizing a narrative synthesis of the findings to emphasize this often-overlooked issue and raise awareness within the scientific community about the need for further research in this area.

3. Results

3.1. Challenges of dental and periodontal treatment in smokers and benefits of quitting

Smoking alters the periodontal microbiota, weakens the immune-inflammatory response to oral biofilm, and compromises healing, leading to less favorable periodontal treatment outcomes. Studies report that smoking negatively impacts non-surgical periodontal therapy including professional mechanical plaque removal/PMPR, periodontal regeneration, and gingival recession coverage [25–31]. Smokers also experience reduced healing potential, leading to lower reductions in periodontal pocket depth and reduced levels of attachment gain post-treatment [32]. Additionally, plaque and calculus re-accumulate more rapidly in smokers than in non-smokers [33], necessitating more frequent supportive care visits (Fig. 1).

However, some studies suggest no significant differences in periodontal therapy outcomes between smokers and non-smokers [34,35]. These inconsistencies may arise from cross-sectional study designs, which do not establish causality, or patient-related factors such as the Hawthorne effect, and adherence to treatment.

The esthetic benefits of PMPR are short-lived in smokers due to the rapid reappearance of extrinsic staining and tooth discoloration caused by nicotine and tar residues in tobacco smoke [36]. Given the accelerated deterioration of periodontal health and dental aesthetics in smokers, modified supportive care strategies are required. Oral health-care professionals should implement individualized recall schedules, recommending check-ups every 3–4 months instead of the standard 6-month interval. Adjunctive therapies, such as antimicrobial mouthwashes and laser therapy, may help manage bacterial load [20].

Ultimately, the integration of tailored smoking cessation programs into periodontal care plans remains the most effective strategy for improving oral health outcomes in smokers. Brief cessation advice at the point of care can be highly impactful. The WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control recommends that dental practitioners implement short interventions for smokers, as even a three-minute counseling

session can increase quit rates by 30 %, particularly when supported by pharmacological and behavioral strategies [24]. In addition, smoking cessation interventions delivered in dental settings can lead to significantly higher quit rates compared to usual care, according to a recent Cochrane review [37]. These findings support the role of oral health professionals in providing structured and effective cessation support as part of routine dental care.

Studies confirm that quitting smoking significantly improves periodontal treatment outcomes [20,38–40]. Former smokers generally exhibit better healing than current smokers [41–43]. Additionally, smoking cessation enhances outcomes of regenerative surgical procedures, including grafting, implant placement, and guided tissue regeneration [44,45]. One of the primary benefits of stopping smoking is the restoration of gingival blood flow, which improves oxygen and nutrient delivery for healing. However, evidence on vascular recovery post-cessation remains inconsistent. Some studies report improved vascularization after quitting [46], while others indicate persistent vascular impairment even after 13 years of abstinence [47]. These inconsistencies may be attributed to several factors including baseline oral health status, smoking intensity (i.e., pack-years), as well as vascular assessment methodologies.

Biomarkers can serve as valuable tools for monitoring periodontal disease progression and treatment response. Pro-inflammatory biomarkers such as interleukin-1 beta (IL-1β) and matrix metalloproteinase-8 (MMP-8) have been linked to periodontal tissue destruction and may help assess disease severity and treatment response [48]. A one-year smoking cessation study found a significant reduction in IL-1β levels among quitters compared to persistent smokers [49].

Emerging evidence suggests that smoking is a significant risk factor for dental implant failure due to impaired bone healing and osseointegration. Systematic reviews and meta-analyses confirm that smoking

increases the risk of peri-implantitis, peri-implant bone resorption, and early implant failure [50,51]. The degree of marginal bone loss in the first year was found to be four times greater in smokers than in non-smokers [52]. In addition, heavy smokers experience significantly greater marginal bone loss (>2 mm) within the first five years compared to light smokers or non-smokers [50]. To mitigate implant-related complications in smokers, dental professionals should encourage quitting smoking at least 4 weeks before surgery to improve vascular recovery. Additionally, using rough-surfaced titanium implants, and larger-diameter implants can enhance bone-to-implant contact and osseointegration.

Enhanced postoperative care, including periodic recall visits and rigorous hygiene measures, is essential for preventing peri-implant plaque accumulation [39]. It is also important to emphasize the value of tongue cleaning [53], as it improves the sense of taste, thus providing additional motivation for quitting smoking. Highlighting the enhanced taste perception post-cessation may encourage behavior change.

Smokers generally underestimate the risks associated with tobacco smoking, including periodontal disease, implant failure, and tooth loss [54,55]. This lack of awareness negatively affects oral hygiene habits, preventive care utilization, and adherence to self-care recommendations. Compared to non-smokers, smokers are less likely to use interdental cleaning aids (floss, mouthwash, interdental brushes), further increasing their risk of periodontal disease and peri-implant complications [56]. Furthermore, smokers are less likely to report dental pain or seek preventive care, which contributes to delayed diagnosis and treatment of oral health conditions [56].

Many smokers experience dental anxiety and avoidance behavior, often due to a fear of judgment from dental professionals [57]. Additionally, stress and depression, which are more prevalent among smokers [58], may contribute to neglecting oral hygiene and lower

IMPACT OF SMOKING ON DENTAL TREATMENTS

Fig. 1. The diagram summarizes the main negative effects of smoking on various dental procedures, including periodontal treatment, implant surgery, professional cleaning, and aesthetic treatments. Smoking can compromise healing, reduce treatment efficacy, and increase the need for frequent follow-up care across all clinical areas.

adherence to dental treatment recommendations. Motivational interventions and patient education are critical in addressing these psychological barriers. A patient-centered, non-judgmental approach can foster greater engagement and adherence to oral healthcare, ultimately improving treatment outcomes and overall well-being.

A recent systematic review by La Rosa et al. (2025) underscores that smoking cessation interventions become even more critical for patients with additional risk factors that could compromise oral health outcomes, such as individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus [59]. Integrating cessation support into dental care can improve treatment outcomes and overall health, making it a key consideration for clinicians.

Given the rapid deterioration of periodontal health, increased risk of implant failure, and lower oral health awareness among smokers, tailored management strategies are essential. Dental professionals should implement customized recall schedules with more frequent visits, and supplement adjunctive therapies to control bacterial load. In implant dentistry, smoking is a key contributor to peri-implantitis and bone resorption, necessitating surgical adaptations, strict maintenance protocols, and targeted risk-reduction strategies. Additionally, addressing smokers' limited awareness of oral health through education, behavioral interventions, and comprehensive smoking cessation support is vital. Ultimately, quitting smoking remains the most effective strategy for enhancing periodontal therapy outcomes, improving implant longevity, and promoting overall oral health in this vulnerable group.

3.2. Smoking cessation for smokers with oral health conditions

Dental professionals play a critical role in raising awareness of the oral and systemic health risks associated with smoking while providing consistent support for cessation efforts. Given the addictive nature of tobacco, quitting often requires multiple attempts and long-term strategies for sustained abstinence. Additionally, psychological and behavioral factors, such as stress, ingrained habits, and environmental triggers, increase the risk of relapse [60]. Smoking relapse is particularly common among individuals with depression [61], a condition linked to poor oral health, including periodontal disease [62]. Conversely, individuals with depression may neglect oral hygiene, contributing to the development or worsening of oral diseases.

Smoking is often used as a coping mechanism for boredom, anxiety, depression and stress, including stress directly related to periodontal health [63,64]. This reliance makes cessation efforts more challenging, particularly as many smokers remain unaware of smoking's detrimental impact on their periodontal and overall oral health [65,66]. This lack of awareness can lead to diminished motivation to quit and contribute to the persistently low cessation rates observed in this population [67]. Addressing these barriers requires tailored interventions that incorporate psychological and behavioral support alongside comprehensive education. Empowering patients with knowledge about how smoking undermines the benefits of dental treatment can reinforce their motivation to quit. Additionally, providing point-of-care biofeedback on salivary nicotine metabolite levels may serve as a powerful motivational tool [68].

The 5A's strategy for smoking cessation is widely recommended and can be adopted in patients with dental and periodontal conditions [69]. Systematically identifying all patients who smoke during their dental visits is imperative (ASK). All identified smokers should receive clear and personalized advice emphasizing the benefits of quitting smoking: *"By quitting, you will not only enhance your overall health but also reduce the development/progression of periodontal disease. Did you know that?"* (ADVICE). In this context, digital visualization tools (e.g., quantitative light-induced fluorescence [QLF]) can help motivate patients by displaying real-time images of poor oral hygiene [70,71]. Assessing a patient's readiness to quit smoking is a crucial step (ASSESS) in the cessation process. For individuals not ready to quit immediately, motivational strategies can help lay a foundation for future cessation

attempts. Rather than pressuring patients to quit immediately, it is often more effective to pause and wait until they feel prepared and confident to make a serious quit attempt. In the meantime, smoking reduction strategies can serve as a practical interim approach to gradually encourage abstinence. Dental professionals may also discuss transitioning to less harmful nicotine alternatives, such as e-cigarettes, heated tobacco products, or oral nicotine products. Additionally, emerging tools like digital health applications and wearable devices can provide innovative support for smokers managing oral health challenges. Furthermore, this step could incorporate QLF imaging to quantify dental plaque and staining scores, offering patients visual evidence of their current oral health status and illustrating the potential improvements following smoking cessation [70,71]. For patients ready to quit, dental professionals should collaborate with them to develop personalized cessation plans (ASSIST). These plans may include setting a realistic quit date and identifying strategies for managing withdrawal symptoms, such as cravings, mood changes, and anxiety, all of which are significant risk contributors to relapse. Pharmacotherapy, combined with behavioral support, has proven to be effective in increasing abstinence rates among smokers with periodontal disease [72]. Addressing common concerns like weight gain can also help build patient confidence and adherence to the plan. Schedule regular follow-ups to monitor progress, provide encouragement, and reinforce commitment (ARRANGE). If QLF tools are available, they can be utilized at 4-week to 6-month intervals to track oral health improvements through imaging and quantitative analysis. Comparing current and previous QLF images provides visible proof of oral health recovery, and may strengthen the commitment to smoking cessation. This approach leverages dentistry's ability to offer direct visualization of smoking-related damage, enhancing engagement beyond traditional verbal counseling. By integrating real-time visual evidence into the 5As method, it serves as a powerful motivational tool for patients resistant to quitting. Referral to specialized cessation programs may be beneficial for patients facing significant challenges in quitting.

This structured, stepwise approach has the potential to enhance long-term smoking cessation success. An algorithm for assisting dental patients who smoke is presented in Fig. 2.

A valid alternative to the 5As model is the 3As approach—Ask, Advise, Act—which is widely recommended in the UK and designed for use in time-limited clinical settings. Its main advantage lies in its brevity and positive framing, offering clinicians a simple framework to deliver a consistent message without requiring in-depth discussion. However, in dental care settings, the additional steps of the 5As model—particularly "Assist" and "Arrange"—can provide added value by enabling follow-up and personalized support, leveraging the continuity of care and trust often present in the dentist-patient relationship. In this context, proactively referring patients to more intensive cessation services, such as quitlines, may be most effective when the patient is already highly motivated to quit [73].

In the general population, smoking cessation success rates can be doubled or tripled when counseling is combined with pharmacotherapy such as varenicline [74], cytisine [75], bupropion [76], nicotine replacement therapy (NRT) [77]. NRT include medicinal nicotine patches, gums, lozenges, inhalers, and nasal sprays. Each form presents distinct advantages and considerations to suit personal preferences. Despite promising outcomes, research on the effectiveness and tolerability of drugs for smoking cessation in individuals suffering from periodontal disease remains limited.

For individuals with periodontal disease who smoke, only limited recommendations can be made for NRT and bupropion due to insufficient evidence, much of which is derived from small or uncontrolled trials. In a retrospective study of 218 dental patients who used pharmacotherapy for smoking cessation, the nicotine patch was the most commonly employed method, followed by nicotine gum, bupropion, and nicotine lozenges [78]. After the smoking cessation intervention, 27 patients (12.4 %) stopped smoking while 74 patients (34.0 %) reduced

Fig. 2. This flowchart outlines the decision-making process for smoking cessation, relapse management, and harm reduction in dental and periodontal care. The approach begins with identifying smoking behavior, providing personalized advice, and assessing readiness to quit. A supportive, non-judgmental strategy highlights the benefits of cessation, such as reduced inflammation, improved healing, and microbiome restoration. For those not ready to quit, harm-reduction strategies (e.g., smoking reduction, alternative nicotine products) are considered. For those ready, a quit plan combining counseling and pharmacological support is recommended. In case of relapse, re-engagement and referral to specialized services are advised.

smoking. A multicentre prospective smoking cessation intervention study in a dental setting using NRT, resulted in a biochemically confirmed abstinence rate of 32.8 % at month 12 [79]. The highest abstinence rate was observed in patients receiving implant treatment (42.9 %), followed by those with potentially malignant oral disorders (37.1 %) and periodontal disease (21.1 %). In a small smoking cessation study of 39 smokers willing to quit (the majority of whom had periodontal disease), an 8-week intervention combining individual counseling with NRT and/or bupropion led to 44 % (17 participants) self-reporting smoking abstinence [72]. However, at 6 months, only 15 % (6 participants) had confirmed continuous smoking abstinence. In a prospective cohort study of 49 smokers with chronic periodontal disease undergoing smoking cessation counselling, different cessation aids were prescribed [80]; 6 patients used bupropion, 27 used NRT, 3 used both bupropion and NRT, and 13 received only counselling. Quit rates were 29 % at 6 months and 25 % at 12 months, with 41 % (20 participants) withdrawing by month 12. In a RCT of 118 periodontal patients attending an outpatient dental hospital, 10 % of those using NRT quit smoking at 6 months, compared to 5 % in the control group [81]. At 12 months, the quit rates were 7 % and 4 %, respectively.

Oral healthcare professionals should consider safety precautions when prescribing smoking cessation medications. NRT should be used with caution in patients with acute cardiovascular events (recent myocardial infarction, severe arrhythmias, unstable angina, or accelerated hypertension). Bupropion is contraindicated in those with seizure disorders, a history of anorexia or bulimia, or those discontinuing benzodiazepines, barbiturates, or antiepileptic drugs abruptly. Since nicotine is a vasoconstrictor that temporarily reduces oral blood flow and may delay healing [82,83], NRT could theoretically slow recovery. However, because NRT delivers significantly lower nicotine levels than smoking, its impact on healing is minimal.

There is insufficient high-quality research on the effectiveness of NRT and bupropion in smokers with periodontal disease. Additionally, there is no clinical data on varenicline and cytisine for this population. Some evidence suggests that varenicline may influence microvascular function, but its specific effects on oral circulation remain unclear [84]. Well-designed, controlled studies are urgently needed to generate stronger evidence and provide more definitive guidance on effective smoking cessation strategies for this population.

Although the general efficacy of smoking cessation pharmacotherapies such as NRT and bupropion is well established, their implementation in patients with periodontal disease may present unique challenges. Oral formulations of NRT or side effects like dry mouth associated with bupropion could affect tolerability and adherence in individuals with existing oral conditions [85,86]. Therefore, the focus should shift from testing efficacy to optimizing the application of these interventions in dental settings, promoting personalized approaches that consider both medical and dental factors to enhance compliance and outcomes.

Even though many smokers are aware of the health risks associated with smoking, including its long-term systemic effects, this awareness often does not translate into motivation to quit. For such individuals, dental professionals can play a crucial role by shifting the focus toward the immediate and visible consequences of smoking—such as tooth discoloration, bad breath, and gum recession—which may be more personally relevant and emotionally compelling, especially among younger patients. In these cases, harm reduction strategies may represent a realistic and patient-centered alternative to complete cessation. Non-combustion nicotine products, for example, have been associated with reduced impact on oral health and improved dental aesthetics, including noticeably whiter teeth compared to conventional cigarettes, as highlighted in recent research [13]. Emphasizing these concrete and

visible benefits can help engage patients who may not respond to traditional health-based messaging alone, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of smoking interventions within dental care settings.

3.3. Alternative strategies for managing smokers with oral health conditions

While complete smoking cessation remains the primary goal in reducing periodontal risk, harm reduction strategies can represent a valuable approach not only for individuals who aim to quit, but also for those who are unwilling or not yet ready to stop smoking entirely [87]. Nicotine alternatives—such as e-cigarettes (ECs), heated tobacco products (HTPs), and oral nicotine pouches (ONPs)—are increasingly recognized as harm reduction tools that may help reduce exposure to harmful substances in smokers who are not responsive to conventional cessation methods or who prefer a gradual transition toward quitting. Despite not being entirely risk-free, ECs expose users to significantly fewer toxic substances than combustible cigarettes [88–90]. Studies suggest that switching from smoking to ECs may lead to early improvements in cardiovascular and vascular health, including reductions in blood pressure and heart rate [91–93].

However, the long-term impact of these changes remains unclear. Regulatory bodies, including the US FDA, have recognized ECs as a harm reduction option [94], and the UK's National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) has endorsed their use [95], emphasizing that nicotine-containing ECs are likely to be far less harmful than continued conventional tobacco smoking. Cochrane systematic reviews, meta-analyses and umbrella reviews suggest that ECs may be more effective than other smoking cessation aids [96,97].

A pilot study by Holliday et al. investigated the use of e-cigarettes as a cessation aid in smokers undergoing periodontal therapy. Patients receiving standard care plus e-cigarettes showed a higher 6-month abstinence rate (15 %) compared to those receiving standard care alone (5 %), suggesting that integrating e-cigarettes into periodontal treatment may enhance quit outcomes [98].

Other non-combustible nicotine products, such as HTPs and ONPs, are also emerging alternatives. A randomized controlled trial assessing HTPs in combination with counseling found a 39 % smoking abstinence rate at three months [99]. Additionally, an open-label study on nicotine pouches demonstrated a self-reported 7-day smoking cessation rates of 27 % after one week, followed by six weeks of sustained use [100].

Beyond their potential role in smoking cessation and harm reduction, emerging evidence highlights their effects on oral health parameters. A recent study using light-induced fluorescence technology demonstrated that dental plaque accumulation in exclusively EC or HTP users was significantly lower than in smokers, suggesting a potential benefit for oral hygiene [7]. Furthermore, even if the use of ENDS may be associated with some negative effects on periodontal health when compared to non-smokers or former smokers, clinical outcomes in ENDS users remain consistently more favorable than those observed in tobacco smokers [101]. Additionally, research on tooth discoloration parameters indicated that both ECs and HTPs result in less discoloration compared to conventional cigarettes [13]. While these findings are promising, robust clinical evidence on the role of alternative nicotine products in smoking cessation among individuals with periodontal disease remains limited. Further well-designed trials are needed to assess their long-term impact. A multicenter RCT is currently underway to provide deeper insights into these effects [102]. Similar to NRT, the nicotine released by ECs or HTPs may theoretically slow healing due to its vasoconstrictive effects. However, since ECs and HTPs deliver significantly lower nicotine exposure than conventional smoking, their impact on healing is likely to be less severe. Dental professionals should be informed about these alternatives and provide balanced, evidence-based guidance on harm reduction strategies when advising patients on smoking cessation [103].

In addition to pharmacological approaches, health interventions delivered using digital and mobile devices are emerging as valuable

tools for smoking detection and cessation. These include smartphone applications, portable carbon monoxide (CO) monitors, and wearable devices that provide real-time feedback and personalized support to users attempting to quit [104,105]. Advances in wearable sensor technology, artificial intelligence, and behavioral tracking have shown promise in enhancing smoking cessation efforts. Mobile applications such as SmokeBeat, SmokeWatch, and Pivot integrate real-time CO monitoring with behavioral interventions, helping users become more aware of their smoking patterns while reinforcing positive behavior change [106–108]. These tools can also improve engagement and adherence, extending the reach and effectiveness of smoking cessation programs beyond traditional clinical settings. Integrating remote CO monitoring into smoking cessation programs could provide significant benefits for individuals with oral health conditions, much like remote glucose monitoring supports diabetes management. Continuous tracking of smoking behavior, coupled with personalized digital interventions, may contribute to improved oral health outcomes by mitigating smoking-related damage [109,110]. Given the potential of digital health solutions, further research is needed to assess their effectiveness, particularly in smokers with periodontal disease, who may derive substantial benefits from targeted, technology-driven cessation strategies.

4. Limitations

Although this work does not follow a systematic review methodology, its primary goal was to offer a comprehensive and updated overview of the implications of smoking in the context of dental treatments, particularly in periodontology. Given the lack of a narrowly defined research question and the broad nature of the topic, a narrative approach was deemed more appropriate. Nevertheless, this preliminary review lays the groundwork for future investigations and could support the development of a systematic review focused on a specific clinical question identified through this initial exploration.

5. Concluding remarks

The dual challenge of managing oral health conditions such as periodontal disease in smokers presents a significant public health concern, demanding a multidisciplinary approach that integrates periodontal care, smoking cessation, and patient education. The synergistic effects of smoking and periodontal disease create a highly destructive environment that not only accelerates disease progression but also compromises treatment outcomes. Addressing these challenges requires tailored interventions that go beyond conventional periodontal therapy, incorporating personalized biofeedback behavioral support, adjunctive treatments, and harm reduction strategies.

Evidence consistently shows that smoking cessation remains the most effective strategy for improving periodontal health, implant success rates, and overall oral health outcomes. While pharmacological aids such as NRT, varenicline, and cytisine offer viable cessation options, their effectiveness in individuals with periodontal disease requires further investigation. Additionally, alternative nicotine products, such as e-cigarettes and heated tobacco products, may serve as harm reduction tools for those unable to quit smoking through conventional methods, although their long-term effects on oral health remain an area of ongoing research.

Beyond pharmacological interventions, innovative digital health technologies, including smoking detection apps, remote carbon monoxide monitoring, and wearable devices, offer promising avenues for enhancing smoking cessation efforts in dental settings. These tools could play a pivotal role in improving patient engagement, adherence, and long-term success in quitting smoking.

The promotion of an interdisciplinary collaboration is crucial for optimizing smoking cessation efforts. Stronger partnerships between dental and medical professionals can promote a more integrated approach to patient care, ensuring that smoking cessation support is

consistently reinforced across different healthcare settings. The establishment of standardized referral pathways, interdisciplinary training programs, and shared intervention strategies would facilitate a more cohesive and effective response to tobacco use, leading to better patient outcomes.

Ultimately, dental professionals are uniquely positioned to drive smoking cessation efforts by integrating evidence-based interventions into routine periodontal care. A structured, stepwise approach can significantly enhance the effectiveness of cessation strategies, ensuring that smokers receive comprehensive support tailored to their individual needs. Future research should prioritize longitudinal studies to assess the impact of smoking cessation and harm reduction strategies on oral health outcomes, providing stronger evidence to guide clinical practice.

By bridging the gap between oral healthcare and tobacco control, we can mitigate the impact of smoking on periodontal disease, improve patient-centered care, and ultimately contribute to better long-term health outcomes for this vulnerable population.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jan Kowalski: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Giusy Rita Maria La Rosa:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Andrea Di Stefano:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation. **Deborah Gangi:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation. **Vaibhav Sahni:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Hasan Guney Yilmaz:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Valeriu Fala:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Renata Górska:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Francesco Saverio Ludovichetti:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Amaliya Amaliya:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Diala Alghalayini:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Meiram Raganin:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Iain Chapple:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision. **Baek Il Kim:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision. **Riccardo Polosa:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

JK, GRMLR, ADS, DG, VS, HGY, VF, RG, FSL, AA, DA, MR, and BIK declare no conflict of interest.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: IC provides consulting advice to various oral healthcare companies, including Unilever, Philips, Haleon, P&G, Johnson & Johnson. RP is full tenured professor of Internal Medicine at the University of Catania (Italy) and Medical Director of the Institute for Internal Medicine and Clinical Immunology at the same University. He has received grants from U-BIOPRED and AIR-PROM, Integral Rheumatology & Immunology Specialists Network (IRIS), Global Action to End Smoking (previously known as “Foundation for a Smoke Free World”), Pfizer, GlaxoSmithKline, CV Therapeutics, NeuroSearch A/S, Sandoz, Merck Sharp & Dohme, Boehringer Ingelheim, Novartis, Arbi Group Srl., Duska Therapeutics, Forest Laboratories and Ministero dell’Università e della Ricerca (MUR) Bando PNRR 3277/2021 (CUP E63C22000900006) and 341/2022 (CUP E63C22002080006), funded by NextGenerationEU, the European Union (EU) economic recovery package. He is founder of the Center for Tobacco Prevention and Treatment (CPCT) at the University of Catania and of the Center of Excellence for the Acceleration of Harm Reduction at the same university. He receives consultancy fees from Pfizer, Boehringer Ingelheim, Duska Therapeutics, Forest Laboratories, CV Therapeutics, and Sermo Inc. He is being paid textbook royalties from Elsevier. He is also involved in a patent application for ECLAT Srl. He is a pro bono scientific advisor for Lega Italiana Anti Fumo (LIAF) and

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